

Review Article

Combating Antimicrobial Resistance through Medicinal Plants: Current Advances and Research Gaps

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Abstract: Antimicrobial resistance (AMR) is a rapidly escalating global health threat driven by antimicrobial misuse, inadequate infection prevention, limited diagnostics and the evolutionary adaptability of microbes. The World Health Organization (WHO) recognizes AMR as a top global public health and development challenge, estimating that bacterial AMR was directly responsible for millions of deaths in last decades. In parallel with management and the development of new antibiotics, medicinal plants and their bioactive constituents are receiving renewed attention as sources of novel antimicrobials and as “antibiotic adjuvants” that restore the activity of existing drugs. Recent advances include improved characterization of plant secondary metabolites, identification of efflux pump inhibitors and biofilm disruptors, synergistic combinations with antibiotics and the integration of plant-derived compounds into nano formulations to enhance delivery and potency. However, despite extensive *in vitro* evidence, translation into clinically validated therapies remains limited by challenges in standardization, reproducibility, pharmacokinetics, safety evaluation, regulatory pathways and sustainable sourcing. Present work synthesizes current scientific advances in plant-based strategies against AMR, critically evaluates strengths and limitations of existing evidence and highlights priority research gaps that must be addressed to move from promising laboratory findings to safe, effective and scalable interventions.

Keywords: Antimicrobial resistance, medicinal plants, multidrug resistance, One Health, phytochemicals

Introduction

Several decades ago, human societies maintained a closer ecological alignment with nature and a deeper understanding of sustainable living (Raatikainen et al., 2024). However, rapid technological advancement, combined with the excessive and often indiscriminate use of both natural and synthetic products, has progressively disrupted this balance (Thomford et al., 2018). The overexploitation of natural resources typically results in slow, cumulative environmental impacts, whereas the misuse of synthetic products often leads to immediate and severe adverse consequences (Lampert, 2019). One of the most critical outcomes of these practices is antimicrobial resistance (AMR) which has emerged as a major global threat to human health, animal health and ecosystem integrity. AMR arises when microorganisms evolve mechanisms that reduce or eliminate their susceptibility to antimicrobial agents, rendering standard therapies increasingly ineffective and leading to prolonged illness, higher healthcare costs and elevated morbidity and mortality (Jacobowski et al., 2025). The widespread misuse and overuse of antibiotics in human medicine, veterinary practice, agriculture and environmental settings have accelerated the emergence of resistant pathogenic strains. Recognizing the interconnected nature of these drivers, global responses to AMR are increasingly framed within a “One Health” approach that integrates human, animal and environmental health (Patra et al., 2025). The World Health Organization (WHO) continues to emphasize that inappropriate antimicrobial use is a principal driver of resistance, while simultaneously underscoring the urgent need for innovation in prevention, diagnostics and therapeutic development (Capuozzo et al., 2024). The development of new antimicrobial agents is a lengthy, complex and resource-intensive process, whereas the loss of efficacy of existing drugs due to resistance can occur rapidly. As a result, the identification of novel and effective antimicrobial strategies has become an urgent global priority (Salam et al., 2023). In this context, medicinal plants have gained renewed attention as promising resources in the fight against AMR. Plants synthesize a vast array of secondary metabolites including alkaloids, terpenoids, phenolics, flavonoids, tannins, coumarins and quinones that have evolved as chemical defences against pathogens and herbivores, providing a chemically diverse and largely untapped reservoir of bioactive compounds beyond conventional synthetic libraries (Sarojini et al., 2025). Importantly, many plant-derived compounds act on multiple microbial targets or modulate microbial physiology rather than exerting a single, lethal mode of action, potentially reducing the selective pressure that drives resistance development. In addition to their direct antimicrobial activity, plant metabolites can function as resistance-modifying agents by inhibiting efflux pumps, disrupting biofilm formation, attenuating virulence factors and enhancing host-pathogen interactions. Such properties enable plant compounds to act as adjuvants that restore or potentiate the efficacy of existing antibiotics, a strategy increasingly highlighted in contemporary AMR research (Angelini, 2024). Present review adopts a broad perspective on combating AMR by synthesizing current advances in: (i) plant-derived antimicrobial agents active against multidrug-resistant (MDR) bacteria and fungi, (ii) plant-based adjuvants that reverse resistance or synergize with conventional antibiotics, (iii) anti-biofilm and anti-virulence strategies and (iv) enabling technologies including omics approaches, computational screening and nano delivery systems that are accelerating discovery and translation. Finally, the review identifies key research gaps and challenges that must be addressed to facilitate the development of clinically viable, plant-based interventions against AMR.

Global AMR landscape and the urgency for complementary solutions

AMR is not a single disease but a systemic risk that undermines modern medicine, affecting routine surgeries, cancer chemotherapy, neonatal care and management of chronic infections. WHO's AMR fact sheet highlights the scale of the problem and the need for coordinated action. In addition to the long-recognized crisis of MDR bacterial pathogens, resistant fungal infections are rising and biofilm-associated infections remain notoriously difficult to eradicate. While new antibiotics are critically needed, the development pipeline is slow and economically challenging and resistance can emerge even to newly deployed drugs. Recent news coverage highlights that new antibiotic approvals can be important breakthroughs, yet they do not eliminate the broader systemic drivers of resistance or the need for additional strategies. Consequently, complementary approaches, antibiotic adjuvants, anti-virulence therapies, improved infection control and alternatives that reduce antibiotic demand are increasingly central to AMR strategies. Plant-derived compounds may contribute to this portfolio, particularly when positioned as resistance modulators or topical/local therapies where high concentrations can be achieved (Prestinaci et al., 2015).

Mechanisms of antimicrobial resistance: key targets for plant-based interventions

Resistance mechanisms are typically grouped into several categories: (1) drug inactivation (β -lactamases), (2) target modification (altered penicillin-binding proteins and ribosomal changes), (3) reduced permeability and altered influx (Porin loss), (4) active efflux of drugs via transporter proteins, (5) bypass of inhibited pathways and (6) physiological tolerance mechanisms such as biofilm growth and persister cells. Among these, efflux pumps and biofilms are particularly attractive targets for plant-derived resistance modulators because they are often broad-spectrum contributors to multidrug resistance. Efflux pumps are membrane transporters that expel diverse compounds, lowering intracellular antibiotic concentrations and enabling survival at drug levels that would otherwise be lethal. Plant polyphenols and alkaloids frequently appear in this context, with evidence for direct pump inhibition, membrane effects, or downregulation of efflux gene expression depending on compound and organism (Gaurav et al., 2023). Biofilms are structured microbial communities encased in an extracellular matrix that limits antibiotic penetration, alters microenvironmental conditions and promotes horizontal gene transfer. Many plant-derived compounds disrupt quorum sensing, reduce extracellular polymeric substance formation or increase biofilm susceptibility to antibiotics, indicating that anti-biofilm action can function as an AMR-relevant strategy even when direct bactericidal activity is modest (Sharma et al., 2023).

Medicinal plants as sources of direct antimicrobials: evidence and limitations

A major body of literature documents antibacterial and antifungal activity of plant extracts and isolated constituents against clinical isolates, including MDR (Multi-Drug Resistant) strains. Contemporary reviews describe plant-derived antimicrobials as acting through membrane disruption, enzyme inhibition, interference with DNA replication, inhibition of protein synthesis and oxidative stress induction, among other mechanisms. Extracts often demonstrate broad activity because they contain

multiple compound classes; however, this complexity is a double-edged sword. While multi-component mixtures may reduce the chance that a microbe can resist via a single mutation, mixtures also complicate standardization, quality control, mechanistic attribution and regulatory approval. In practice, plant extracts vary with species identity, plant part, harvest season, geography, soil conditions, drying ways, storage methods and extraction solvent (Plate 1). Two studies testing “the same” plant can produce different minimum inhibitory concentrations (MICs) because the chemical profiles differ. For this reason, the field is moving toward chemical characterization and identification of active markers to enable reproducible formulations.

Plate 1: Some common medicinal plants; a) *Abrus precatorius*, b) *Abutilon indicum*, c) *Alangium salviifolium*, d) *Albizia lebbek*, e) *Allophylus serratus*, f) *Artabotrys hexapetalus*, g) *Barleria prionitis*, h) *Barringtonia acutangula* and i) *Bombax ceiba*

Even so, isolated compounds can sometimes lose potency relative to the parent extract if synergy among constituents is important, meaning that both approaches single molecules and standardized mixtures remain relevant depending on intended use (Plate 2). A pragmatic translational pathway for direct plant antimicrobials may be strongest in topical, localized or device-related applications where high local concentrations are feasible and systemic exposure is limited. Systemic therapy, while possible, imposes much higher requirements for pharmacokinetics, toxicology, multidrug interaction assessment and manufacturing consistency (Hashempur et al., 2025).

Antibiotic potentiation and synergy: plants as resistance-modifying agents

One of the most promising AMR-relevant roles for plant compounds is not to replace antibiotics outright, but to enhance them. Antibiotic potentiation includes restoring activity against resistant strains, lowering

the effective dose required and reducing the likelihood of resistance emergence by hitting multiple pathways simultaneously. Recent literature continues to emphasize combination therapy strategies and highlights phytochemicals as candidates for combinational approaches (Angelini, 2024). Synergy can occur through several mechanisms. Plant compounds may increase membrane permeability, allowing greater antibiotic influx. They may inhibit efflux pumps, raising intracellular antibiotic concentration. They may disrupt biofilms and thereby permit antibiotic penetration. They may inhibit resistance enzymes or interfere with stress responses that enable survival under antibiotic pressure. In some cases, plant compounds weaken virulence programs, improving host clearance and reducing the bacterial load that antibiotics must eliminate. However, synergy claims are often overstated in the literature due to methodological issues. True synergy is ideally demonstrated using standardized checkerboard assays with fractional inhibitory concentration indices, time-kill kinetics and replication across multiple clinical isolates. Many papers rely on zone-of-inhibition changes that can be influenced by diffusion properties rather than genuine pharmacodynamic interaction. A key research need is robust, harmonized synergy testing frameworks that permit comparison across studies.

Plate 2: Some common medicinal plants; j) *Careya arborea*, k) *Celastrus paniculatus*, l) *Clitoria ternatea*, m) *Dillenia pentagyna*, n) *Dioscorea pentaphylla*, o) *Ehretia aspera*, p) *Phanera vahlii*, q) *Piliostigma malabaricum* and r) *Psydrax dicoccos*

Efflux pump inhibition: a central and evolving theme

Because efflux contributes to multidrug resistance across many pathogens, EPIs are a major focus of plant-based AMR research. A comprehensive review of efflux pump inhibitor discovery describes EPIs as potential adjuvants and explicitly includes plant-derived EPIs among the potentiators under investigation. More recent work continues to explore specific natural molecules and combinations as

efflux modulators, including alkaloids and polyphenols with diverse structural features (Zhang et al., 2023). Polyphenols are frequently cited for efflux-related activity. Many studies and reviews discuss alkaloids as particularly effective candidates, often tied to efflux inhibition and combinational therapy concepts (Duda-Madej et al., 2025). Despite strong conceptual appeal, translating EPIs into therapies is challenging. Many EPIs are “promiscuous” membrane-active compounds that can also affect human transporters, raising toxicity and multidrug interaction concerns. Efflux pumps belong to different families and inhibitors may be pump-specific or organism-specific. Therefore, the field increasingly needs (i) target validation in clinically relevant strains, (ii) selectivity profiling against human transporters, (iii) pharmacokinetic matching to partner antibiotics and (iv) demonstration of benefit in animal infection models.

Anti-biofilm and anti-virulence strategies: reducing pathogenic fitness without strong selection for resistance

Biofilm and virulence interference is an attractive AMR strategy because it may exert lower selective pressure than direct killing, potentially slowing resistance evolution. Plant-derived quorum sensing inhibitors, biofilm matrix disruptors and adhesion blockers have been described across many systems. By reducing toxin production, motility, adhesion and biofilm formation, these agents can make pathogens more susceptible to antibiotics and immune clearance (Zhao et al., 2020). The challenge is that anti-virulence endpoints are harder to standardize than MIC values. Biofilm assays vary widely and virulence regulation depends on growth conditions and host-like signals. Additionally, anti-virulence agents may show organism-specific activity and may not translate from laboratory strains to clinical isolates. A major gap is the need for clinically relevant biofilm models, including polymicrobial biofilms, host-mimicking media and integration with immune components (Mirghani et al., 2022).

Enabling technologies accelerating discovery from medicinal plants

Modern plant-based AMR research increasingly combines classical ethnopharmacology with advanced analytical chemistry, computational screening and systems biology. Metabolomics and LC-MS/MS can profile extracts and correlate chemical features with bioactivity, enabling bioassay-guided fractionation that is more efficient and reproducible. Genomics and transcriptomics in pathogens can reveal whether a plant compound downregulates efflux genes, suppresses virulence networks or triggers stress responses. These tools are particularly helpful for complex extracts, where activity may not map to a single molecule (Najmi et al., 2022). In parallel, computational approaches are being applied to predict binding to efflux pump targets, identify drug-like natural product derivatives and prioritize compounds for synthesis and testing. Systematic reviews are also being designed to map dual efflux inhibitory activity across antibacterial and cancer MDR contexts, reflecting increasing methodological rigor in how resistance-modifying compounds are identified and categorized.

Plant-based nano formulations and “nano-green” approaches

Nanotechnology is reshaping antimicrobial delivery and can potentially address AMR by improving drug penetration into biofilms, increasing local concentration at infection sites and enabling controlled

release. Plant-derived compounds can be encapsulated in liposomes, polymeric nanoparticles, nanoemulsions or other carriers to enhance solubility and stability. Another major area is “green synthesis” of metallic nanoparticles using plant extracts, which can act as reducing and capping agents (Mohanta et al., 2023). Plant-mediated green synthesis is appealing because it can reduce reliance on harsh chemicals and may yield nanoparticles with unique surface chemistry influenced by phytochemicals. Reviews of plant-based silver nanoparticle synthesis emphasize how phytochemicals influence formation and biological activity. Broader AMR-focused nano formulation reviews also discuss nanocarriers and plant-based compounds as part of emerging “nanoantibiotic” strategies (Alsaiani et al., 2023). Nonetheless, nanoparticle approaches introduce additional safety and regulatory complexity. Metallic nanoparticles can have cytotoxicity, immunological effects and environmental persistence concerns. Their antimicrobial action can be non-specific, raising the risk of collateral damage to beneficial microbiota or host tissues depending on route and dose. Reproducibility is also a challenge: “green synthesis” outcomes can vary with plant extract composition, reaction conditions and purification methods. Therefore, rigorous physicochemical characterization, standardized manufacturing protocols and *in vivo* safety studies are essential before these approaches can be deployed widely (Parvin et al., 2025).

Evidence beyond the petri dish: in vivo studies, clinical data and translational realities

A central limitation of plant-based AMR research is the large gap between *in vitro* activity and clinical utility. Many compounds show MICs in the tens to hundreds of micrograms per millilitre, which may be unrealistic systemically. Others are potent *in vitro* but poorly bioavailable, rapidly metabolized or highly protein-bound. Plant compounds may also induce or inhibit human drug-metabolizing enzymes and transporters, complicating co-administration with antibiotics (Rossiter et al., 2017). *In vivo* studies are improving but remain uneven. Some plant-derived agents show efficacy in animal infection models, especially topical or gastrointestinal models where local exposure is high. Yet many published studies lack appropriate comparators, do not confirm target engagement or do not evaluate resistance emergence over treatment. Clinical trials for plant-derived antibacterials or adjuvants remain relatively sparse compared with the scale of *in vitro* research. Moving forward, the field needs a translational pipeline that prioritizes candidates with (i) strong potency and selectivity, (ii) feasible delivery routes, (iii) safety margins, (iv) manufacturability and (v) clear mechanisms linked to AMR reduction.

Safety, toxicity, herb-drug interactions and microbiome considerations

A common misconception is that “natural” equals “safe.” Many plant secondary metabolites are bioactive precisely because they interact strongly with biological systems. Alkaloids, for example, can be pharmacologically potent and toxic depending on structure and dose. Polyphenols are often considered safer but can still affect enzymes and transporters and high doses may cause gastrointestinal or hepatic effects in some contexts. When plant compounds are used as antibiotic adjuvants, interaction risks increase because antibiotics may already have narrow therapeutic windows or specific metabolic pathways (Tan et al., 2022). Another emerging consideration is the microbiome. Broad-spectrum antimicrobials whether synthetic or plant-derived can disrupt gut and skin microbiota,

potentially promoting opportunistic infections or resistance gene exchange. Anti-virulence or narrow-spectrum approaches may be less disruptive, but this must be tested empirically. Future research should routinely include microbiome impact assessments, especially for oral/systemic therapies (Li et al., 2025).

Standardization, quality control and regulatory pathways

For medicinal plants to contribute meaningfully to AMR control, products must be consistent, safe and efficacious. This is a major bottleneck. Standardization requires validated botanical identification, control of contaminants and chemical fingerprinting with defined marker compounds and acceptable ranges. Extract manufacturing must follow good manufacturing practices and stability over shelf life must be demonstrated (Vaou et al., 2021). Regulatory classification matters. A plant product marketed as a dietary supplement faces fewer requirements but cannot ethically substitute for antimicrobial therapy. A plant-derived drug or adjuvant intended to treat infections must meet rigorous standards similar to pharmaceuticals, including preclinical toxicology, clinical trials and post-market surveillance. If positioned as an antibiotic adjuvant, regulatory evaluation must also consider the combination product how the plant compound affects antibiotic pharmacokinetics, toxicity and resistance dynamics (Alostad et al., 2020).

Sustainability, access and ethical dimensions

Scaling plant-based solutions raises sustainability and equity issues. Overharvesting of wild medicinal plants can threaten biodiversity and local livelihoods. Cultivation, tissue culture and synthetic/semisynthetic production of active compounds can mitigate pressure on wild resources, but these approaches require investment and capacity building. Ethical sourcing and benefit sharing are critical, especially when ethnomedicinal knowledge informs discovery. In AMR, where global need is high, equitable access to any successful plant-derived therapies is essential, aligning with the broader “one health” approach and global governance goals emphasized in quadripartite AMR frameworks (Chen et al., 2016).

Major research gaps and priorities

A consistent theme across modern reviews is that plant-derived antimicrobials and adjuvants are promising but limited by translation barriers. The most urgent gaps can be summarized in narrative form as follows (Anand et al., 2019). First, there is a reproducibility and comparability gap. Studies often use different extraction methods, different strains and different assays, leading to results that cannot be reliably compared or meta-analyzed. Harmonized protocols for MIC testing, synergy assessment and anti-biofilm evaluation plus sharing of raw data and chemical fingerprints would substantially improve evidence quality (Guzmán-Soto et al., 2021). Second, there is a mechanism-validation gap. Many papers propose mechanisms without direct evidence in clinically relevant strains or without confirming that the mechanism explains synergy *in vivo*. Mechanistic work should integrate genetics, transcriptomics and target engagement assays to confirm causality rather than correlation (Floris et al., 2018). Third, there is a pharmacokinetics and formulation gap. Numerous plant compounds have poor

solubility and bioavailability. Formulation science including prodrugs, salt forms, encapsulation and local delivery systems must be integrated early, not treated as an afterthought once a compound “works” *in vitro* (Żyżelewicz and Oracz, 2022). Fourth, there is a safety and interaction gap. Systematic toxicology, transporter/enzyme interaction profiling and microbiome impact studies are often missing. This is especially critical for efflux pump inhibitors, because selectivity against bacterial pumps versus human transporters will determine whether an EPI is a useful adjuvant or an unacceptable risk (Dodd and Cann, 2022). Fifth, there is a clinical evidence gap. The field needs well-designed animal models and human clinical trials that test plant-derived candidates as adjuncts or therapeutics using clinically meaningful endpoints, including cure rates, time to clearance, relapse and resistance emergence. Candidates that show strong topical efficacy, device-associated infection prevention or gut-localized activity may be the most feasible early wins (Mukherjee et al., 2022). Sixth, there is a manufacturing and regulatory gap. Many promising findings do not progress because researchers lack pathways or partnerships for GMP production, stability testing and regulatory submissions. Interdisciplinary collaboration among botanists, chemists, pharmacologists, clinicians and regulatory scientists is needed to create development-ready candidates (Herdiana, 2025). Finally, there is a sustainability gap. Research programs should incorporate sustainable sourcing plans and consider cultivation or synthetic routes early, particularly for plants that are slow-growing, rare or harvested destructively.

Future outlook: how medicinal plants can realistically contribute to AMR control

In the near term, medicinal plants are most likely to contribute to AMR control through three translationally practical avenues. The first is antibiotic adjuvants that reverse resistance mechanisms such as efflux and biofilms, thereby extending the life of existing antibiotics, an approach consistent with the broader push for innovative strategies beyond simply discovering new antibiotic classes. The second is topical and localized therapies for skin, wound, oral and device-associated infections, where exposure and efficacy are easier to achieve and monitor. The third is formulation-driven innovation, including plant-derived nano formulations and green-synthesized antimicrobial nanoparticles, provided safety and reproducibility challenges are addressed with pharmaceutical rigor (Murugaiyan et al., 2022). Importantly, plant-based strategies should not be framed as a substitute for antimicrobial stewardship, vaccination, sanitation, diagnostics and infection prevention. Rather, they are a potentially valuable component of a diversified AMR response. WHO’s continuing emphasis on coordinated action and measurable targets reinforces the need for solutions that are not only scientifically interesting, but scalable, safe and integrated into health systems.

Conclusion

Medicinal plants offer a rich reservoir of chemical diversity with significant potential to address AMR through direct antimicrobial activity, resistance modulation, efflux pump inhibition, biofilm disruption and virulence attenuation. Modern analytical and biological tools are improving the rigor of plant-based AMR research, while nano formulation and green nanoparticle synthesis are expanding delivery and potency possibilities. Yet the field remains constrained by variability of plant materials, insufficient standardization, limited mechanistic validation, gaps in pharmacokinetics and toxicology and a shortage

of robust *in vivo* and clinical evidence. Closing these gaps requires a translational mindset, prioritizing candidates with realistic delivery routes, quantifying synergy using standardized methods, validating mechanisms with modern molecular tools and developing reproducible formulations under quality-controlled manufacturing. With these steps, medicinal plants can move from promising laboratory findings to clinically meaningful interventions that complement stewardship and strengthen global capacity to manage resistant infections.

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